

Malon-*m*-anisidic Acid and some of its Derivatives

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In earlier communications^{1,2,3} we described the preparation of malon-*p*-phenetidic acid, malon-*o*-anisidic acid and some of their derivatives and also of some new coumarins.

The present communication deals with the preparation of malon-*m*-anisidic acid, its ethyl ester and acid hydrazide. The malon-di-*m*-methoxy anilide was also obtained during the preparation of the above acid. The acid was condensed with benzaldehyde and salicylaldehyde. A trace of pyridine was found the best catalyst for these condensations. Benzaldehyde gives both benzylideno-malon-*m*-anisidic acid and cinnam-*m*-anisidide, whereas salicylaldehyde gave coumarin-3-carboxy-*m*-anisidide. Further, from malon-*m*-anisidic acid hydrazide, the hydrazones of benzaldehyde, *o*-methoxy, *o*-nitro and *p*-chlorobenzaldehydes, salicylaldehyde, 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde, 2-thiophenylaldehyde, furfuraldehyde and acetophenone were prepared in good yields. The hydrazide thus could be used as a reagent for the detection of carbonyl compounds.

EXPERIMENTAL

The methods followed for the preparation of the following compounds were the same as described earlier¹ for the derivatives of *o*-anisidine.

Malon-*m*-anisidic Acid and Malon-di-*m*-anisidide. Starting with *m*-anisidine (12.3 g., 1 mol.) and ethyl malonate (24 g., 1.5 mol.), malon-*m*-anisidic acid was obtained as a white crystalline product (8.3 g.), m.p. 96°. (Found: N, 6.60; C₁₀H₁₁O₄N requires N, 6.609%). Malon-di-*m*-methoxyanilide (10.3 g.), m.p. 150° was obtained. (Found: N, 9.03; C₁₇H₁₉O₄N₂ requires N, 8.90%).

Ethyl Malon-*m*-anisidate.—This ester was obtained as a viscous liquid and was used as such in subsequent experiments.

Malon-*m*-anisidic Acid Hydrazide.—Malon-*m*-anisidic acid hydrazide was obtained as a white crystalline substance, m.p. 130°. (Found: N, 18.51; C₁₀H₁₃O₃N₂ requires N, 18.8%).

1. Singhal, O.P., Khetan, S. K. and Ittyerah, P. I., *Jour. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 42, 480.
2. Singhal, O. P. and Ittyerah, P. I., *Ibid.*, 1965, 42, 802.
3. Singhal, O.P. and Ittyerah, P. I., *Ibid.* 1965, 42, 616.

Benzylidene-Malon-m-anisidic Acid and Cinnam-m-anisidide.—Starting from malon-*m*-anisidic acid (1 g.) and benzaldehyde (.54 g.), benzylidene-malon-*m*-anisidic acid (.48 g.), m.p. 177°(d) (Found: N, 4.42; C₁₇H₁₆O₄N requires N, 4.71%) was obtained.

Cinnam-*m*-anisidide (.98 g.), m.p. 124° (Found: N, 5.78; C₁₆H₁₃O₂N requires N, 5.53%) was obtained when pyridine was used as a condensing agent.

Coumarin-3-carboxy-m-anisidide.—Coumarin-3-carboxy-*m*-anisidide (.38 g.), m.p. 188° was obtained by heating malon-*m*-anisidic acid (1 g.) and salicylaldehyde (.58 g.) in presence of a trace of pyridine at 105° for 4 hrs. (Found: N, 4.77; C₁₇H₁₃O₄N requires N, 4.70%).

Malon-m-anisidic Acid Hydrazones.—Several hydrazones were prepared and Table I gives the yield, m.p., analytical results etc.

TABLE I

Malon- <i>m</i> -anisidic acid hydrazone of	Formula	M.P. (°C.)	Yield (%)	Nitrogen%	
				Found	Required
Benzaldehyde.	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₂	190	64	13.67	13.5
<i>o</i> -Methoxy-benzaldehyde.	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₂	162	62	12.72	12.31
<i>p</i> -Chloro-benzaldehyde.	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	222	60	12.40	12.15
<i>o</i> -Nitro-benzaldehyde.	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₄	183	20	16.26	15.73
Salicylaldehyde.	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₂	199	30	13.10	12.84
5-Chloro-salicylaldehyde.	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₂ Cl	184	30	11.87	11.61
2-Thiophenylaldehyde.	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₂ S	158	30	13.51	13.24
Furfuraldehyde.	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₂	166	23	14.50	13.95
Acetophenone.	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₂	176	37	13.09	12.92

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